

IMPROVEMENT OF THE SOFTWARE FOR DETERMINING THE RATING OF PROFESSORS-TEACHERS IN A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION

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Abstract: *This article provides detailed information about the improvement of the software for determining the rating of professors and teachers of the higher education institution, the State Inspection of Education Quality Control under the Cabinet of Ministers carried out certain works in this regard, and various methods.*

Key Words: *Indicator, integration, hierarchical, synchronous, asynchronous.*

At the meeting held under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on October 24, 2018, dedicated to the issues of further development of the higher education sector, it was decided to expand international cooperation to further improve the national rating system, use rating indicators aimed at more scientific activities, and employers was given a task to introduce indicators for evaluating integration relations between higher educational institutions.

The State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education under the Cabinet of Ministers has carried out certain activities in this regard. In particular, the experience of South Korea, Japan, China, Malaysia, England, Russia and the style of prestigious rating agencies such as QS (Quacquarelli Symonds), ARWU (Academic Ranking of World Universities), THE (Times Higher Education) were studied. Higher education institutions of Uzbekistan were compared and analyzed with rating indicators. Based on this, an updated rating structure was created that evaluates the activities of national higher education institutions in Uzbek language. This, in turn, creates a basis for achieving high indicators in the local rating system, recording the names of Uzbekistan's higher education institutions in the international arena, and entering the prestigious rating list of world universities.

draft decision of the Cabinet of Ministers was developed on the improvement of the procedure for determining the rating of higher education institutions based on the results of the experiment and the

international criteria of the prestigious rating agencies . This decision approves the regulation on the procedure for determining the rating of higher education institutions and the improved rating structure. This document was submitted to the Cabinet of Ministers for approval in agreement with relevant ministries and agencies.

The State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education is the only impartial organization that monitors the quality of education of local higher education institutions in Uzbekistan and helps them to take a worthy place in the list of international rating agencies in the future. cooperates with prestigious international rating agencies.

Four different indicators are used according to the methodology of the QS company: the quality of scientific and research work, the level of need for graduates, the quality of teaching, the internationalization of education (internationalization).

These indicators are rated as follows:

- academic reputation of the university - 40 percent (in order to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of the university's scientific research activities, field scientists, researchers and professors-teachers up to rectors are involved in the survey);
- the reputation of the university among employers - 10 percent (here, what kind of personnel the university produces, the demand for them is evaluated based on a survey conducted among employers);
- professor-teacher-student ratio — 20 percent (the number of students per teacher);
- the rate of citations from the published scientific articles of the professor-teacher — 20 percent (the number of citations corresponding to one teacher);
- share of foreign teachers - 5 percent;
- the share of foreign students is 5 percent.

In order to determine the reputation of universities through the survey, QS divides them into five areas: arts and humanities, life and biomedical sciences, social sciences, natural sciences and technology .

In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 08.10.2019 No. PF-5847 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", the systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan the process of setting priorities, training independent thinking highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high spiritual and moral qualities is qualitatively new upgrading, modernization of higher education,

development of social sphere and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies, were defined as the goals and tasks of the higher education system. One of these tasks consists of "- determining the necessary measures to control the quality of education and create a non-state system of rating higher education institutions." Based on this task, a system for determining the rating of professors was developed. In order to ensure the implementation of the above-mentioned government decisions, systematic work is being carried out to determine the rating of professors and teachers in the higher education institutions of our Republic. There is an "Independent Evaluation Aggregator of Higher Education" for the implementation of evaluation and rating systems of Russian State Universities at the international level. There are independent experts in the evaluation of universities and they carry out evaluation covering all areas of universities. The determination of the ranking of professors and teachers of higher education institutions and their digitization leads to the increase of the capacity of personnel in higher education institutions and competition among professors and teachers. As a result, our main goal is to further develop students' knowledge and potential. In addition, when the rating system is open to all, positive competition will develop between professors and teachers, it will be possible to determine the position of professors and teachers in HEIs, and the rating of departments. As a result of the determined rating, professors and teachers start monitoring themselves. Such rating systems are constantly used in countries with developed educational systems. The goals and objectives of the system offered by us are as follows:

- Monitoring of dissertations defended by professors;
- Electronic monitoring of the list of scientific articles published by professors and teachers;
- Forming and monitoring the electronic list of financial funds received by foreign and national scientific research centers;
- Forming a list of inventions, useful models and received copyright certificates made by professors and teachers;
- Forming an electronic list of teachers and students of foreign countries;
- Determining the ranking of professors and teachers of the university;
- Determination of internal inter-faculty ranking of the university;
- Monitoring the University's ranking and growth rates over the years.

We develop and monitor this rating based on about 30 criteria. In short, the main goal of the developed system is to automate the work of the

educational quality control department. It creates an opportunity to transparently evaluate the rating of each professor by the head of the department, the dean's office and the management of the higher education institution.

Serious reforms are underway in higher education systems aimed at encouraging institutions to be more responsive to the needs of society and the economy. This was accompanied by a reassessment of the goals of higher education and the development of new government strategies. Although institutions now there is more room for maneuver for institutions, they also have clearer accountability to society. It is expected that the tertiary sector will contribute to equality, ensure quality and work efficiently

Knowing the impact of using active learning methodologies in higher education requires not only determining the quality of acquired competencies by analyzing and interpreting the learning results of students, but also knowing their impact on future professional activities. perceptions of students, employers and professionals themselves.

Given that the primary goal of higher education is to make students active agents, independent and responsible for their own learning, professors should encourage students' self-directed and self-efficacy processes and should be able to evaluate. The importance of assessment, self-evaluation, regulation, and self-regulation to enhance learning dictates the need to monitor the use and quality of these processes through meta-evaluation.

Given this framework and society, which is uncertain and unstable due to constant change, it is urgent to have a dynamic pedagogical assessment of professors who can interpret the signs of the times. To solve this problem, our goal is to create strategic mechanisms to adapt to the new reality, to develop plural and multifaceted competences in professors, and to create a combination of efforts in both professional and interpersonal relations between people and institutions. At a high level, it will be appropriate to overcome the emerging needs together. Now, according to the above, this implies the provision of professional harmony and coherence necessary for the reflective capacity of professors. Based on the mentioned points, we felt the need to communicate with the professors, to understand their concerns, fears, uncertainties and to implement it among peers, because it does not exist in practice or is very new compared to the accepted methodology.

The general and widespread understanding of pedagogical supervision considers it a set of actions or procedures for monitoring pedagogical practice and "mainly a process in which an experienced and knowledgeable teacher leads another teacher or another teacher." candidate teacher in their personal and professional development". The control function establishes a differential relationship between supervisor and supervisee, which, according to control models used in practice, is a difference between the most asymmetric and serious hierarchical extreme and the other extreme can do, the hierarchical distinction becomes more blurred, tending to be more egalitarian.

Implementation of pedagogic control procedures in HEIs derives from political and organizational orientations, which presupposes that quality and student-centered teaching of HEIs depends on supervision. It appears that, in light of the latest definitive guidance on building successful HEIs, "the quality of the HEI organization and those who carry out their teaching, training or support work encouraging and monitoring its development" they explained.

But if the figure of the leader disappears and the hierarchy of control is in favor of learning through cooperation with peers, then a more democratic relationship, implemented in the concrete context of the pedagogical practice of the participants, also plays an important role. We emphasize that the goals of improving education and training should not be lost, the quality of the higher education institution that empowers them, the functions of systematic and continuous monitoring, reflection and guidance of pedagogical practice should not be lost. Faculty members with professional expertise in such goals can perform such functions through peer interactions in the context of their daily collaborative teaching practice. It involves and enables self-observation and professional evolution, resulting in improved student learning.

an artificial hierarchical structure, dialogic, formative, teacher and student problem solving should be focused on, daily peer collaboration through individual and collective thinking is a form of peer interaction. is more conducive to improving teaching and learning conditions. To supervisory practices that affect only certain learning activities and do not interact with the HEI environment to which all school members and peers belong.

WebQDA® software supports qualitative data analysis in a collaborative and distributed environment. Although there are some software packages that address non-digital and unstructured data (text,

images, video, audio) in qualitative analysis, few researchers can use them in a collaborative work environment and in the way that the Internet can offer. can be distributed. It is software aimed at researchers in a variety of contexts who need to analyze qualitative data individually or collaboratively, synchronously or asynchronously. The software follows the systematic and theoretical design of other software available on the market, and differentiates itself by providing online, real-time collaboration and research support service (webQDA®, 2018).

Considering the objectives of the study, we tried to provide a detailed and rigorous description to guarantee the validity or reliability of the qualitative study. Some authors "point to the need to establish certain strategies. Among them, we emphasize the triangulation of various collected sources, that is, they approach the same phenomenon from different perspectives. We also emphasize the triangulation of data. we chose to focus on "the modality that proves that the collected data is confirmed by another (theoretical) source, and we refer to the transparency of the whole process, which guarantees the reader the importance, reliability and trustworthiness of the data.

"How to Evaluate Peer Interaction as an Alternative Process for Evaluating Teaching Effectiveness?" When we try to answer the question. We clearly hypothesized that currently, the area where evaluation teams outside of Higher Education institutions should focus their efforts to improve their performance and self-evaluation reporting is "teaching monitoring and control" should be. classroom practice, professional development strategies and supporting reflection in teaching practice. In this regard, we argue that peer interaction work is in no way inconsistent with this assumption of external assessment, as the assessment network's proposal is clearly concerned with professional development, reflection, and improvement clearly informed by peer feedback. shown. and as a result, student learning in g class has improved.

The problem is not in creating and implementing a rating system as an incentive to encourage students and teachers to make every effort to constantly improve the quality of work done. What is the quality of student education if the rating system is only a means to achieve it, not the goal? Quality, as you know, is the enemy of massification, the standardization of society and the functioning of the school educational process simply appeals. state standards... And the teacher is a mass profession, and the mass is always heterogeneous compared to the quality. Therefore, many teachers focus on the effect (rating) rather than the cause (increasing the

quality of the student and / or the entire class). The above dilemma shows the need for more thorough promotion and organization of the introduction of the initial stage rating system.

REFERENCES:

1. Alarcão, I., & Roldão, M. (2008). Supervisão: Um contexto de desenvolvimento profissional dos professores [Supervision: A context of professional development of teachers]. Mangualde: Pedago.
2. Alarcão, I., & Tavares, J. (2010). Supervision of pedagogical practice: A perspective of development and learning. Coimbra: Almedina.
3. Amado, J. (2013). Manual de investigação qualitativa em educação [Manual of qualitative research in education]. Coimbra: University of Coimbra.
4. Bardin, L. (2015). Analysis of content [Content analysis]. Lisboa: Edições 70.
5. Guzmán, JC (2018). Buenas prácticas de enseñanza de los profesores de educación superior [Good teaching practices of higher education teachers]. REICE. Revista Iberoamericana sobre Calidad, Eficacia y Cambio en Educación, 16(2), 133-149. <https://doi.org/10.15366/reice2018.16.2.008>
6. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". Tashkent city, October 8, 2019, No. PF-5847
7. Approaches to evaluating teacher effectiveness. Washington, June 2008
8. Medatov AA Online Performance Learning on E-Learning Systems. European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (EJLSS). Volume 12, 2021
9. Pokaseteli otsenki deyatelnosti professorsko-pedovatel'skogo sostava, kafedr i institutov universiteta. Novosibirsk, 2016 5. Rating prepodavat